

ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN
EDUCATION AND EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN
UZBEKISTAN

Abdullajonov Davronjon

teacher of business department of Kokand University,
abdavron94@gmail.com , +998907857557.

Annotation. In this thesis, it was mentioned that today the education system of Uzbekistan and what is the focus of the education system, education is often carried out under the guidance of teachers.

Key personnel: education, personnel, higher education, Bachelor's degree, economics, master's degree, Ministry of Education, report, technology

Enter.

The creation of electronic educational tools for educational subjects further expands the possibility of using modern information and communication technologies in teaching these subjects. This, in turn, is the main factor of students' in-depth acquisition of knowledge in these subjects and increases the quality and efficiency of education.

The implementation of such efforts will further accelerate the wide application of modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process, equip professors and teachers with advanced pedagogical knowledge and technologies, improve their skills, and use the experience of foreign higher education institutions. provides an opportunity for in-depth study and introduction of their effective methods and tools into our national education system. Multimedia is a rapidly developing modern information technology. Its distinguishing features include: it integrates various types of information: traditional (text, tables, decorations, etc.), original (speech, music, excerpts from video films, TV frames, animation, etc.) in one software product.

Such integration is different devices for recording and displaying information, work at a specific time, unlike text and graphics, which are static by their nature, audio and video signals are viewed only at a certain time interval. will be released. The speed of the central processor for processing and displaying video and audio information on the computer, the bandwidth of the data transmission bus, the operating and video memory, large-capacity external memory, the size and the speed of exchange of computer input-output channels by approximately two times needs to be increased, a new level of "human-computer" interactive communication, in which the user receives more extensive and comprehensive information in the process of communication, which allows to improve the conditions of education, work or recreation. Education of students and retraining of personnel on the basis of multimedia tools is an urgent issue of today.

The concept of multimedia entered our lives in the early 90s. What did he ask himself? Many experts analyze this term in different ways. In our opinion, multimedia is an embodied form of delivery of educational materials to students based on audio, video text, graphic and animation effects based on software and technical tools of informatics. The method of teaching in developed countries is currently being applied in the field of education. Not even every family can have fun without multimedia devices. The gross turnover of multimedia tools in 1981 was 4 billion US dollars, and in 1994 it was 16 billion US dollars. Nowadays, it is impossible to imagine every computer sold without multimedia tools.

Attempts to introduce computers in education in the 1970s failed primarily because of their extremely low productivity. Practice shows that teaching students on the basis of multimedia tools is doubly effective and saves time. It is possible to save up to 30% of time in learning based on multimedia tools, and the acquired knowledge is retained in the memory for a long time. If the students accept the given materials on the basis of sight, the retention of information in memory increases by 25-30%. In addition, if educational materials are presented in the form

of audio, video and graphics, the retention of materials in memory increases by 75%.

Teaching students based on multimedia tools has the following advantages:

1) there is a possibility of deeper and more perfect assimilation of the given materials;

2) the passion for close contact with new areas of learning will increase:

3) as a result of reducing the time of education, achieving the opportunity to save time

4) acquired knowledge is kept in one's memory for a long time and it is possible to use it in practice if necessary. Informatics and information technology, as a fundamental science, deals with the development of the methodology for establishing informational provision of management processes with any objects on the basis of computer information systems.

There is also an opinion that one of the main tasks of science is to determine what information systems are, what place they occupy, what structure they should have, how they work, and what laws are characteristic of them. In Europe, the following main scientific directions can be distinguished in the field of informatics: network structure development, computer integrated process production, economic and medical informatics, social insurance and environmental informatics, professional information systems. The emergence of the multimedia system has led to revolutionary changes in several professional fields such as education, science, art, computer training, advertising, technology, medicine, mathematics, business, scientific research.

Although the idea of using computers in the educational system appeared much earlier, the use of information technology in all areas of the educational system became more complete after the advent of computers equipped with multimedia devices. was put into practice

The process of implementation of personalized education with the help of multimedia tools requires the development and use of modern, multi-disciplinary,

subject-oriented multimedia educational tools. They include extensive databases, educational knowledge bases, artificial intelligence systems, expert-learning systems, laboratory practices with the ability to create mathematical models of the studied process and phenomena. According to the possibilities of taking into account the individual characteristics of learners and helping to increase their interest (motivation), as well as according to the qualities of compatibility, interactivity, flexibility of various types of multimedia educational information, multimedia is useful and productive education. In technology. Providing interactivity is one of the important achievements of digital multimedia compared to other means of presenting information. Interactivity refers to providing information relevant to the learner's needs. Interactivity allows you to control the presentation of information to a certain extent: learners can individually change the settings defined in the program, study the results, respond to the program's request about a specific desire of the user, set the speed of presentation of materials and the number of repetitions. possible But it is important to consider a number of aspects when using multimedia. Educational materials presented in multimedia should be easy to understand, presented through modern information and convenient tools. In order to fully reveal all the possibilities of multimedia technologies and use them effectively, students need the support of a potential (competent) teacher.

As with the use of textbooks, in the use of multimedia tools, the educational strategy is enriched with content only when the teacher is engaged not only in providing information, but also in helping, supporting and guiding the learning process. possible Usually, presentations enriched with beautiful images or animations are more attractive than plain text and can provide the necessary emotional level while complementing the material being presented.

EDUCATION MANAGEMENT BODIES

The general management of the education system is carried out by the Cabinet of Ministers. Also, the Cabinet of Ministers directly manages a separate higher

education institution, Tashkent Islamic University, as well as branches of internationally famous foreign HEIs (MSU, Westminster University, etc.).

The direct management of education systems in Uzbekistan is carried out by two ministries - the Ministry of Public Education (MPE) and the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education (EO'MTE).

HTV is responsible for the activities of pre-school, out-of-school institutions and general education schools. There are 5 higher education institutions and 16 institutes for teacher training under the management of HTV. The Ministry has regional, district and city departments of public education that methodologically manage the activities of relevant educational institutions in the areas.

OO'MTV is a state management body that manages higher and secondary special and vocational education in the republic. The Ministry reports to the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in its activities.

The system of the ministry includes the center of secondary special and vocational education, the center of higher and secondary special education, the center of development of vocational education, departmental higher educational institutions.

OzR OOMTV system

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The education of the citizens of our country is guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Education plays an important role in the education of the youth of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Activities in the field of economy, science, technology and culture under the term "Higher education".

References

1. Abdullajonov, D. (2022). Development of the Economy of New Uzbekistan through digital technologies, Perspectives of the Digital Economy: Digital economy, digital technologies, digital Uzbekistan, ICT, "One million programmers", information security, e-commerce. Scientific material base of Kokan University, 1(000006).

2. Abdullajonov, D. (2022). Improvement of socio-economic mechanisms of strengthening the labor motivation of employees in the enterprise: labor motivation, foreign experience, efficiency, corporate systems, innovative economy. Scientific material base of Kokan University, 1(000005).

3. Kasimova, G. Q. Q. (2021). Ways to reduce the level of poverty in our country. Scientific progress, 2(7), 808-816.

4. Appendix 1 "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation". October 5, 2020, No. PF-6079.

5. G. Q. Kasimova, F. M. Mulaydinov. Problems of innovative development in economy and business. Science and culture in the eyes of young scientists and leaders: international scientific and practical online conference, June 26, 2020. - Kokan. Pages 172-174.

6. D.SH. Abdullajonov, G.Q. Kasimova. Broad implementation of digital technologies in the real sector of the economy and in agriculture and water management.